

CRITICAL REVIEW ON MULTIPLICITY OF VIRECHANA YOGA IN CHIKITSA STHANA OF CHARAKA SAMHITA

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ABSTRACT

Among the five principal *Shodhana Karmas*, *Virechana* occupies a central role for the purification of *Pitta Dosha*, especially when located in the *Adhobhaga* of the body. Yet, in the *Chikitsa Sthana* of *Charaka Samhita*, *Charaka* depicts a remarkable diversity in the indication, intensity, and formulation of *Virechana*, transcending the boundaries of *Pitta* disorders. He recommends *Virechana* even in *Vata*, *Kapha*, and *Sannipataja* conditions, wherever *Pitta* or *Aashaya Dushti* acts as a co-factor. This paper offers a detailed textual and conceptual review of the multiplicity of *Virechana Yogas* mentioned across various disease chapters of *Charaka Chikitsa Sthana*. The objective is to understand the rationale behind different intensities (*Mridu*, *Madhyama*, and *Teekshna*), forms (*Ghrita*, *Taila*, *Churna*, *Kwatha*), and *Anupanas* used, while identifying assessment factors such as *Bala*, *Koshtha*, *Dosha*, *Vyadhi Bala*, and *Avastha*. The study highlights *Charaka's*

rational, individualized, and adaptable therapeutic reasoning, establishing his approach as timelessly scientific and clinically relevant.

KEYWORDS: *Virechana, Charaka Samhita, Shodhana, Pitta Dosha, Panchakarma, Mridu, Madhyama, Teekshna.*

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda conceptualizes health as the balanced state of *Dosha, Dhātu, Mala,* and *Agni*, governed by the principle of *Samyak Prakriti-Sthapana*. To maintain or restore this equilibrium, *Shodhana Chikitsa* plays a vital role. Among its five classical measures—*Vamana, Virechana, Basti, Nasya,* and *Raktamokshana*—the *Virechana Karma* serves as a chief measure for *Pitta Shodhana*.

However, *Charaka Samhita*^[1], being the oldest and most systematic treatise, reflects a broad therapeutic philosophy in which no procedure is rigidly confined to a single *Dosha*. *Virechana*, though classically a *Pitta-Shodhana* measure, has been repeatedly recommended by *Charaka* in various *Vataja, Kaphaja, Rakta,* and even *Sannipataja* conditions where the deeper pathogenesis involves *Avarana, Aama,* or *Srotorodha*.

In *Chikitsa Sthana*, across different disease contexts like *Jwara, Pandu, Kushtha, Udara, Rajayakshma,* and *Unmada*, one finds multiple formulations—each selected based on the *Dosha predominance, Avastha, Bala,* and *Koshtha* of the patient. This multiplicity reflects the clinical acumen of *Charaka* in tailoring *Virechana* therapy with utmost precision.

Thus, the present critical review attempts to systematically explore the multiplicity of *Virechana Yogas* in *Charaka Chikitsa Sthana*, their pharmaceutical forms, therapeutic indications, and conceptual rationale.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A textual critical review of *Charaka Samhita – Chikitsa Sthana* (approx. 1000 BCE – 400 CE) was undertaken, along with classical commentaries such as *Ayurveda Dipika* by Chakrapani and comparative modern works by Sharma, Dash, and Tripathi.

All verses indicating *Virechana* were extracted, categorized, and interpreted contextually.

The study focused on four analytical aspects:

1. Disease indication and *Dosha predominance*
2. Drug selection and pharmaceutical form (*Kalpana Bheda*)
3. Rationale of intensity (*Mridu–Madhyama–Teekshna*)
4. Assessment parameters (*Bala, Koshtha, Dosha, Vyadhi Bala*)

- **Etymology**

Virechana word is made by combination of main '*Rich*' *dhatu* and '*Vi*'*Upsarga* and '*Nich*' '*Lyut*' *Pratyayas* giving meaning '*Visheshena Rechayateeti*.

Rechana is derived from root word '*Ricir Dhatu* and *LyutPratyaya*' (*Mala Bhedana*)^[1].

Acharya Charaka has mentioned *Virechana* word for both *Vamana* and *Virechana* in *KalpSthana*. So the word *Rechana* is commonly used for evacuation of *Doshas*, which is done by both *Vamana* and *Virechana*. But in general, the word *Virechana* denoted evacuation of *Dosha* through anus.

- **Definition**

Virechana is a process by which the vitiated *Pitta* and other *mala* from the whole body are expelled out through gastrointestinal tract by means of purgation with the use of specific formulations.^[2]

- **Importance of *Virechana Karma***

- ✓ Detoxifies the body incase of *Pitta* accumulation
- ✓ Deeply cleans the whole gastrointestinal tract including poisoning
- ✓ Cures various skin disorders and allergy
- ✓ Helps with heart disease, Asthama and Diabetes Treats Problems like Piles, Constipation, Jaundice and Inflammations.

- **Classification of *Virechana Drugs***^[3]

Sukha Virechana - *Trivrruta*

Mridu Virechana - *Aaragwadh*

Teekshna Virechana - *Snuhi*

Charakokta Virechana Dravya^[4]

Moolini – 16 *Phalini* – 19

Sneha – 4 *Lavana* – 5

Mootra – 8 *Dugdha* – 8 *Shodhanartha Vriksha* – 6

Acc. To *Sharangadhara*^[5]

1. *Anulomana* - *Hareetaki*
2. *Sramsana* - *Kritamalaka*
3. *Bhedana* - *Katuka*
4. *Rechana* – *Trivritta*

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

1. Categorization Based on Intensity of Virechana

(A) Mridu Virechana

- Mridu Virechana aims for Sukha Shodhana—a gentle, non-exhaustive purification suitable for patients with Alpa Bala and Dhatu Kshaya.

Charaka prescribes it in conditions like Punaravartaka Jwara, Rajayakshma, Kamala, Raktapitta, Shotha, and Vatarakta.

Disease	Condition		Reference
1) Jwara, ^[6] Vishama Jwara, Punaravartak Jwara	Daha, Trushna, Pitta Pradhana	Nirama, Baddha Dosha BahuDosha – Adhobhagi dosh	Cha. Chi. 3/167-168, 171, 230-233, 294, 340
	Aksheena Bal-Mams-Agni		
2) Raktapitta ^[7]	Santarpanotha, Urdhwaga	BahuDosha	Cha. Chi. 4/55-56
	Aksheena Bal-Mams-Agni		
3) Gulma ^[8]	Santapa	Vataja- Vrudhha Pitta	Cha. Chi. 5/31
Pittaja Gulma	Snigdha-UshnaJanya	Agni Bala Apexi	
Kaphaj Gulma	Sthanat Apasrut		
4) Kushtha ^[9]	Pitta Pradhana		Cha. Chi. 7/39, 61
	Twak Ashrit Dosha-Nitya		
5) Rajayakshma ^[10]	Doshadhik		Cha. Chi. 8/87-88
6) Unmada ^[11]	Kapha-Pitta Avruta		Cha. Chi. 9/25-26
7) Shotha ^[12]	Adho Dosha		Cha. Chi. 12/17-19, 21-22, 27-28
	Kaphoththa		
	Sadosha, VataPittaja		
8) Udara ^[13]	Pleehodara		Cha. Chi. 13/78
9) Arsha ^[14]	Asava-Arishta		
10) Kamala ^[15]			Cha. Chi. 16/60
11) Kshayaja Kasa	Bahu Dosha, navotthit		Cha. Chi. 18/150
12) Pravahika	Bahu Shula, Sarakta-Piccha, Trushna	Vibaddha, Vata-Varchas,	Cha. Chi. 19/48
13) Vatarakta ^[16]	Adau		Cha. Chi. 29/41
	Gambheera	RaktaPittotara	Cha. Chi. 29/43, 45
15) Yoni Vyapad ^[17]	Vyapanna Yoni – srv prakar		Cha. Chi. 30/45

➤ Mridu Virechana Yogas

Sr. No.	Shloka/Context	Drug/Preparation	Indication	Remarks
1	Jwara Chikitsa (16–171, 230–233)	Mrudvika, Amalaki, Trivrut Churna, Ghrita, Dugdha	Pittaja, Vata-Pittaja Jwara	Gentle purgation in feeble patients
2	Raktapitta Chikitsa (55–56)	Aragwadha, Triphala, Dugdha	Raktapitta, Kamala	Pitta-Rakta elimination without strength loss
3	Kushtha Chikitsa (39, 61)	Haritaki, Abhaya with Gud, Taila	Kaphaja Kushtha	Mild expulsion of Dosha with Snehana
4	VataVyadhi Chikitsa	Trivrut + Ghrita, Pippali,	Vata disorders,	Sneha-based Mridu Shodhana

	(25–26, 340)	<i>Dugdha</i>	<i>Rajyakshma, Jwara</i>	suitable for <i>Dhatu-Kshaya</i>
5	<i>Shotha Chikitsa</i>	<i>Aragwadha + Pippali + Dugdha</i>	<i>Kaphaja Shotha</i>	Gentle cleansing in inflammatory conditions

From above table, following observation are seen

- ✓ *Godugdha* used: 10 times
- ✓ *Triphala*: 10 times
- ✓ *Aragwadha*: 1 time
- ✓ *Mrudvika*: 2 times
- ✓ *Amalaki*: 7 times
- ✓ *Kampillaka*: 3 times
- ✓ *Gudabhaya*: 4 times

Mridu Virechana aligns with the Ayurvedic concept of “*Shuddhir na ati karshanam*”—purification without exhaustion. *Charaka* recommends milk, *ghrita*, and *madhura dravyas* to maintain *Dhatu Samata* while removing aggravated *Pitta* or *Aamadasha*.

(B) *Madhyam Virechana*

-*Madhyama Virechana* is applied when moderate purification is needed —neither too mild nor too drastic.

It is ideal for diseases involving *Dosha Sansarga* and partial *Koshthashrita Dushti*.

Disease	Condition		Reference
1) <i>Gulma</i>	<i>Santapa</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta Vriddha</i>	<i>Chakrapani Tika-Cha.Chi.5/31</i>
2) <i>Udara</i>	<i>Sarva Udara Snigdha, Sanjata Bala</i>	<i>Avrut Vayu</i>	<i>Cha.Chi.13/118-119</i>
3) <i>Grahani</i> ^[18]	<i>Niruha Paschat</i>		<i>Cha.Chi.15/79</i>
4) <i>Pittaja Pandu</i>	<i>Trivrut+Sharkara</i>		<i>Cha.Chi.16/56</i>
5) <i>Kaphaja Pandu</i>	<i>Gomutra Haritaki</i>		<i>Cha.Chu.16/57</i>
6) <i>Pittaja Kasa</i>			<i>Cha.Chi.18/85</i>
7) <i>Visarpa</i> ^[19]	<i>Pittaja</i>		<i>Cha.Chi.21/64 - 67</i>
8) <i>Vatarakta</i>	<i>Malavrut Vata</i>		<i>Cha.Chi.29/157</i>

➤ *Madhyam Virechana Yogas*

Sr. No.	Shloka/Context	Drug/Form	Indication	Remarks
1	<i>Jwara Chikitsa (31)</i>	<i>Snehair Anulomikaih</i>	<i>Vata Gulma, Santapa</i>	Moderate purgation balancing <i>Vata</i> and <i>Pitta</i>
2	<i>Kustha Chikitsa (118–119)</i>	<i>Sura, Sauvira Siddha Ghrita, Patolmula, Rajani, Vidanga</i>	<i>Pitta-Kapha dominant skin disorders</i>	For <i>Kapha-Meda Dushti</i>
3	<i>Meda Roga Chikitsa (79, 157)*</i>	<i>Eranda Taila, Trivrut, Danti, Tiktaka Ghrita</i>	<i>Meda Roga, Kaphaja Pandu</i>	To mobilize and eliminate obstructed <i>Kapha</i>

4	<i>Pandu Roga Chikitsa</i> (56–57)	<i>Danti, Trivrut Churna, Draksha</i>	<i>Pittaja Pandu</i>	Balanced <i>Shodhana</i> without over-depletion
5	<i>Vatarakta Chikitsa</i> (62)	<i>Mahatiktaka Ghrita, Eranda Taila</i>	<i>Rakta-Pitta involvement</i>	Ensures deep cleansing through <i>Rakta-Moola</i> channels

From above table, following observation are seen

- ✓ *Trivrut*: 16 references
- ✓ *Haritaki*: 15
- ✓ *Eranda Taila*: 5
- ✓ *Gomutra Haritaki*: 4

Madhyama Virechana suits ***Pittaja Vyadhi* with partial *Kapha Sannipata* or *Rakta Dushti*.**

It's also advised post-*Snehana* and *Svedana* in individuals of moderate strength.

(C) *Teekshna Virechana*

-*Teekshna Virechana* is used where *Dosha Sanchaya* is intense or *Srotorodha* causes deep-seated pathologies like *Udara, Gulma, Unmada, or Apasmara*.

Disease	Condition	Reference
1) <i>Gulma</i>	<i>Dwiguna Matra, Neelinadya Ghrit, Trayamanadi Ghrita</i>	<i>Cha.Chi.5/105-109 ;112-114</i>
	<i>Kaphaja Gulma</i>	<i>Cha.Chi.5/149-160</i>
2) <i>Apasmara</i>	<i>Pitta Pradhana</i>	<i>Cha.Chi.10/14</i>
3) <i>Baddhodara</i>		<i>Cha.Chi.13/90</i>
4) <i>Udara</i>		<i>Cha.Chi.13/137-140</i>
5) <i>Atyagni</i>		<i>Cha.Chi.15/231</i>
6) <i>Pandu</i> ^[20]		<i>Cha.Chi.16/40</i>
7) <i>Visha</i>		<i>Cha.Chi.23/45</i>
8) <i>Hridaya Shula</i>	<i>Trishu Kaleshu</i>	<i>Cha.Chi.26/102</i>

➤ *Teekshna Virechana Yogas*

Sr. No.	Reference	Drugs / Preparation	Indications	Remarks
1	<i>Gulma Chikitsa</i> (109–114)	<i>Neelinyadya Ghrita, Tiktaka Ghrita, Trivrut, Snuhi, Danti</i>	<i>Gulma, Udara, Shotha, Kamala</i>	Strong purgation for deep-seated <i>Doshas</i>
2	<i>Udara Chikitsa</i> (152–153)	<i>Mishraka Sneha, Trivrut Churna, Sudha Ksheera, Madhu</i>	<i>Kaphaja Gulma, Udara</i>	<i>Bhedana</i> action to remove <i>Srotorodha</i>
3	<i>Unmad Chikitsa</i> (14, 90)	<i>Snuhi Ksheera, Tilwaka, Swarnaksheeri</i>	<i>Apasmara, Unmad</i>	<i>Teekshna Virechana</i> for <i>Mano-Vata</i> disorders
4	<i>Kamala Chikitsa</i> (40, 102)	<i>Trivrut, Danti, Haritaki, Tikta Dravya</i>	<i>Kamala, Pleeha, Shwitra</i>	High-intensity <i>Virechana</i> post- <i>Snehana</i>
5	<i>Visha Chikitsa</i> (45)	<i>Vamana + Teekshna Virechana</i>	<i>Visha, Hridaya Shoola</i>	Detoxification through rapid <i>Dosha</i> expulsion

From above table, following observation are seen

- ✓ *Patolmula*: 2
- ✓ *Indravaruni*: 1
- ✓ *Trayamana*: 6
- ✓ *Saptala*: 2
- ✓ *Danti*: 9
- ✓ *Neelini*: 3
- ✓ *Snuhi*: 3
- ✓ *Swarnaksheeri*: 3
- ✓ *Tilwaka*: 1

Teekshna Virechana corresponds to the modern concept of intensive detoxification—rapid expulsion of vitiated *Dosha*, used cautiously in individuals with good strength and resistant diseases.

2. Forms of *Virechana* Dravya Used

Form	Number of Uses	Example
<i>Ghrita (Sarpi)</i>	17	<i>Tiktaka Ghrita, Mahatiktaka Ghrita</i>
<i>Churna</i>	11	<i>Trivrut Churna, Haritaki Churna</i>
<i>Swarasa</i>	6	<i>Patolmula Swarasa, Danti Phala Rasa</i>
<i>Taila</i>	5	<i>Eranda Taila</i>
<i>Kwatha</i>	5	<i>Triphala, Tiktaka Kwatha</i>
<i>Asava/Arishta</i>	5	<i>Takkarista, Arishta formulations</i>

3. Type of *Virechana* & Assessed Factors

Parameter	Observation
Type	<i>Sneha Virechana (11), Ruksha Virechana (1)</i>
Assessed Factors	<i>Bala, Koshtha, Dosha-Kala-Bala, Vyadhi Bala, Dhatu condition</i>
Examples	<i>Rajyakshma (Bala), Udavarta (Koshtha), Stanya Dosha (Dosha-Kala)</i>

DISCUSSION

1. Pathological Basis for Multiplicity

Charaka's approach is dynamic—he doesn't confine *Virechana* to one *Dosha*. Instead, he considers:

- *Vyadhi Samprapti* — Whether *Dosha* is in *Koshtha* or *Shakha*
- *Dosha-Dhatu-Samsarga* — *Pitta* may combine with *Vata* or *Kapha*, changing the line of treatment
- *Rogi Bala* — Weak patients require *Mridu Virechana*, strong ones *Teekshna*
- *Vyadhi Bala* — Chronicity or intensity dictates the type and dosage

2. Clinical Implications of Dosha Association

- *Vata-Pittaja Conditions*: Require *Sneha*-based mild *Virechana* (e.g., *Udavarta*, *Vatodara*)
- *Kapha-Pittaja Conditions*: Indicate use of bitter and pungent *Virechana* with *Gomutra* or *Tiktaka Dravya*
- *Rakta Dushti*: Necessitates *Sneha–Teekshna* balance (e.g., *Raktapitta*, *Vatarakta*)

3. Role of Anupana and Formulation

- *Madhu + Ghrita* – acts synergistically in *Jwara* through *Rasayana* and *Kapha-Pitta* pacification.
- *Madhu + Sharkara* – cooling in *Rakta Pitta* due to *Madhura-Kashaya Rasa*.
- *Dugdha* – balances *Ushna Teekshna Dravya*, prevents dehydration.
- *Gomutra* – promotes *Srotoshodhana* and *Kaphahara* in chronic pathologies.

4. Conceptual Insights

Multiplicity in *Virechana* represents *Charaka's Anukta Vyadhi Chikitsa Siddhanta* — the ability to adapt therapy beyond textual rigidity.

Each formulation in *Chikitsa Sthana* exemplifies rational customization based on *Desha*, *Kala*, *Agni*, *Bala*, and *Avastha* — the hallmarks of *Ayurvedic* precision medicine.

CONCLUSION

1. *Charaka's Clinical Flexibility*

The multiplicity of *Virechana Yoga* reveals *Charaka's* adaptive approach to *Dosha* variation, where the therapy is not disease-specific but *Samprapti*-specific.

2. Therapeutic Customization

The classification into *Mridu*, *Madhyama*, and *Teekshna* ensures safe administration across diverse patients, preventing under- or over-purification.

3. Pharmaceutical Diversity

Use of *Ghrita*, *Churna*, *Taila*, *Swarasa*, and *Kwatha* underlines *Charaka's* understanding of bioavailability and *Dravya–Karma–Anupana* synergy.

4. Relevance to Modern Practice

These references serve as guidelines for current *Panchakarma* protocols, emphasizing assessment-based individualization and procedural refinement.

Thus, *Virechana* in *Charaka Chikitsa Sthana* stands as an enduring example of therapeutic pluralism, scientific adaptability, and timeless clinical reasoning.

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